

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FALOLOU****FIRST NAME: SEGUN ROCKER****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 3%

The author used the following software: (MS Word – Office 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401 D

1. What is the first step for using Zotero?

- Add sources to your Zotero Library
- Install the browser Connector
- Open a Word document and use the Zotero tab for in-text citations and references
- Download and install the desktop App.¹**

2. What is Grammarly helpful to correct in the text?

- The spelling²**

¹ Steven Bradburn, How to use Zotero: A complete Beginner's Guide (YouTube, Feb 25, 2023), 12:40 min, https://youtu.be/JG7Uq_JFDzE.

² Stacey Roshan, Grammarly Tutorial: Making Use of Grammarly Premium and an overview of Grammarly for Google Docs (Youtube, Oct 16, 2018), 07:29 min, <https://youtu.be/FKRBvTOLo1M>.

- Only the synonyms
 - The plagiarism
 - Only the sentence structure
3. What are the different steps for starting an academic essay?
- Finding and writing the question-Doing researches-Defining a definitive plan
 - Proposing a plan-Defining the question-Writing a draft
 - Reading, researching-Defining the question and analyzing the task-Drafting an initial plan³**
 - Defining the question-proposing a plan-doing research
4. What are the two kinds of citation entries in an academic essay?
- The in-text citation and the out-text citation
 - The in-text citation and the bibliographic entries⁴**
 - The reference entries and the bibliographic entries
 - The footnotes entries and the endnotes entries
5. What are the right bibliographic entries for this book, as far as Turabian rules are concerned?
- Turabian, Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for writers of research papers, theses, and dissertations*. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.⁵**

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7.

⁴ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 173.

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 171.

- Turabian, Kate L. 2018. A Manual for writers of research papers, theses, and dissertations. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press. The reference entries and the bibliographic entries
 - Turabian, Kate L. A Manual for writers of research papers, theses, and dissertations. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press. 2018
 - Turabian, Kate L. 2018. “A Manual for writers of research papers, theses, and dissertations.” 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
6. What is the correct citation in-text as far as Turabian rules are concerned?
- (Turabian, 2018. 243-300)
 - (Turabian 2018. 243-300)
 - Turabian, Kate L. 2018. “A Manual for writers of research papers, theses, and dissertations.” 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
 - (Turabian 2018, 243-300)⁶**
7. Are these components the parts of the introduction chapter?
- Statement of the problem/Literature review/Critical review of the literature
 - Statement of the problem/Research questions/Findings/
 - Statement of the problem/Research questions/Social Significance⁷**
 - Research questions/Literature review/Social Significance

⁶ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 243.

⁷ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 27.

8. What assertion about the method chapter is correct?
- The method chapter introduces the problem and the hypothesis of the research
 - The method chapter helps the reader to judge if the method used in the research provided an adequate opportunity to examine the research questions and hypotheses.⁸**
 - The method chapter is the first chapter of dissertation thesis
 - The method chapter determines the problematic of research
9. What assertion is right among these sentences?
- In E.U. systems, the style used for spelling is the North American English form
 - In E.U. systems, the style used for spelling is the Canadian English form
 - In E.U. systems, the style used for spelling is the typical style of the Commonwealth countries
 - In E.U. systems, the style used for spelling is the British form⁹**
10. What are the three central institutions of the E.U., as far as political areas are concerned?
- European Commission, European Council, European Parliament¹⁰**
 - European Council, Court of Justice of E.U., European Economic and Social Committee
 - European Parliament, Court of Justice of E.U., European Court of Auditors

⁸ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 34.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission* (Brussels: European Commission, 2021), 17.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*, 84.

- European Court of Auditors, Central Bank of E.U., Committee of the Regions

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

The University of Chicago. *The Chicago Manual of Style*. Seventeenth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2017.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second ed. Florida: Florida State University, 2017.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D 'Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th Edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

European Union. *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. Eight ed. Brussels: Office of the European Commission, 2021.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.